

The Effects of Asymmetric Satellite Networks on Protocols

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ABSTRACT

The Naval Research Laboratory (NRL) is conducting a simulation and experimental effort to document and optimize the use of Internet Protocol (IP) over satellite based highly asymmetric networks. Within the DoD, the emergence of the Global Broadcast Service (GBS) with its ability to deliver data to the warfighter at data rates approaching 25Mbps is creating unprecedented opportunities. Commercial very small aperture terminal (VSAT) networks, while not typically offering quite as much throughput, often support Mbps capabilities. However, it is often the case that high data rates to the warfighter are not available in the reverse direction. NRL has demonstrated asymmetric networking using GBS as the forward channel and low-cost organic backchannels for the return paths. Typical backchannel solutions include telephone (POTS), cellular phone, satellite mobile phone, commercially available VSAT, UHF FLTSAT, Inmarsat B, and tactical radio. Each of the backchannel solutions presents different data rate capabilities and bit error rates, but typical backchannel data rates range from 1.2Kbps to 160Kbps. A typical GBS or VSAT "forward" channel operates in the 1-5Mbps range. A network built on such asymmetry presents challenges not typical of full duplex physical layer links. NRL has investigated the effect such asymmetry has on TCP, TCP Extended Window Option, Selective Acknowledgements, and reliable multicast. The investigations have

focused on the ability of each to efficiently transfer large data files to the warfighter. The investigative effort began with simulation and experimental efforts to document the effect on forward channel throughput for FTP and HTTP file transfers using backchannels ranging in data rate from 1.2Kbps to 2Mbps. Standard round trip time calculations for throughput based on window size limitations are not adequate for describing performance in highly asymmetric networks. Extended window option and selective acknowledgement enhancements to TCP simulated and experimental results are discussed. The use of reliable multicast to overcome the basic windowing challenges and deliver data to multiple users simultaneously is addressed.

INTRODUCTION

The Naval Research Laboratory (NRL) is involved in a program to investigate and demonstrate asymmetric networking techniques with an emphasis on the use of standards-based commercial network protocols to implement a real-time user-pull / smart-push (WWW browser) Global Broadcast System (GBS) capability. GBS, with its ability to deliver data at rates approaching 25Mbps, provides a new class of service to the warfighter. Combining this data delivery capability into an asymmetric network using organic communications paths provides the warfighter real-time high data rate access to pull information from terrestrial networks (Internet, SIPRNET). The Naval Research Laboratory and the Operational

Figure 1. JWID98 NRL / OSO Asymmetric Network Configuration

Support Office (OSO) of the National Reconnaissance Office (NRO) demonstrated such a capability during JWID98 [1]

As part of a high data rate satellite communications effort funded by the Office of Naval Research (ONR), NRL is attempting to characterize the effect of commercial protocols on asymmetric networks and in particular on the use of GBS as the data delivery channel for an asymmetric network. The effect of long fat networks (LFN), or networks that have the ability to deliver large amounts of data but also have long delays has been well documented [2,3]. The effort described in this paper differs from previous papers addressing LFN is that this work focuses on asymmetric network configurations and in particular GBS. In the GBS environment, a symmetric network is simply not practical. The use of GBS to deliver High Data Rate (HDR) data to the warfighter is a reality. Warfighters often have limited ability to complete the return link and have no ability to

complete it at rates approaching the rates available over GBS.

ASYMMETRIC NETWORK TEST CONFIGURATION

The JWID98 demonstration, diagramed in figure 1, provided NRL an excellent opportunity to gather some statistical information about asymmetric networks.

For the asymmetric network investigations, the GBS Joint Program Office (JPO) allowed NRL access to a 2Mbps data channel on the GBS broadcast. The NRL data stream was broadcast over GBS on a "private" data channel to avoid security and throughput impacts with official GBS data traffic. The GBS broadcast originates from the Pentagon. NRL's network operations center (NOC) delivered the 2Mbps data stream to the Pentagon via satellite from NRL. This arrangement, implemented for expediency, placed a two-hop geostationary satellite delay, approximately 550ms, into the

system before the data reached the GBS receiver. Since the primary goal of the investigative effort was to bound GBS asymmetric network capabilities, initial testing was completed using a hardwired backchannel. This baseline configuration, diagramed in figure

Figure 2. Asymmetric Network Throughput Investigation Block Diagram

2, consisted of the GBS broadcast, originating at NRL, terminating to a GBS receive suit at NRL, hardwired to the GBS broadcast router at NRL.

The use of a "hardwired" backchannel solution ensured an error free link and simulated, in terms of delay, a two-hop satellite configuration, which we believe to be realistic for a deployed warfighter. Backchannel data rates ranging from 1.2Kbps to 2Mbps were tested by controlling the router serial interface, all testing used the 2Mbps GBS "forward" channel.

RESULTS

Results were achieved using a single IP version 4 (IPv4) TCP/IP thread, identical to what ONE typical user could expect during a single FTP, WWW browsing, or similar file transfer. One of the first tests performed was a comparison of FTP and HTTP for a large file transfer. As can be seen in figure 3, for a large file transfer both protocols performed similarly.

Throughput was defined as application layer throughput actually realized by the user. The results have been averaged over a number of file transfers to mitigate channel effects on a single test, however, as can be seen in figure 4,

Figure 3. HTTP vs. FTP throughput in an asymmetric networked environment

throughput remained reasonably consistent over the entire test, indicating a low bit error rate (BER) GBS link. Since for this testing the backchannel is hardwired, this link was assumed to be error free. Figure 4 results are for a backchannel running at 2Mbps. Similar results for other backchannel data rates support the conclusion that the asymmetric network forward channel (GBS) suffered little from bursty or high BER conditions. This conclusion is important in that it suggests that TCP/IP congestion control

Figure 4. Throughput as a function time for HTTP and FTP file transfer.

had little effect on throughput for large file transfers in this test configuration. It is well understood that TCP/IP slow start and congestion control have a major limiting effect on throughput in high BER and long latency environments, however this initial work was designed to mitigate these effects.

Another statistic that was collected during the asymmetric network testing was the router input and output port weighted throughput average. These numbers indicate the average data flow through the router interface. For this

testing the routers were dedicated to the test, attempting to ensure all data flow through the router was relevant. The difference between the application layer throughput and the router interface average data rate is an indication of protocol overhead. These results, indicating a significant percentage of the data through the router was useful user data, further supporting the earlier conclusion that TCP/IP did not spend a statically significant amount of time in a slow start or congestion control state during this testing.

Figure 5. Router interface forward channel (GBS) average data rate during throughput testing.

Perhaps some of the most interesting results are the results indicating what data rate the router needed on the backchannel to support the throughput on the forward channel. This indicates that improvements in the degrees of asymmetry (i.e. increasing the backchannel data rate) will have little effect on single thread TCP/IP throughput, at least in this nearly perfect environment. As figure 6 shows, in the low BER environment TCP/IP required approximately 15-16Kbps to sustain throughput as seen in figures 3 and 4. However, in real-world environments, perfect backchannels are not typical. The JWID98 demonstration [1] provided an opportunity to test the asymmetric network in a more realistic configuration. Quantitative results are not yet available for the "real" asymmetric network backchannels actually implemented, but typical FTP / WWW browsing throughput results of 80 – 200Kbps were achieved, during JWID98, using comparable delays. Backchannel configurations that introduced additional delay, such as those requiring a third satellite hop or adding

significant processing delays, such as UHF DAMA, did not produce comparable results.

Figure 6. Router interface backchannel average data rate during throughput testing.

TCP/IP Extended Windows

Clearly one solution to the LFN problem is RFC 1323, TCP/IP extended windows [4]. NRL has acquired two SUN workstations and two NT5 Beta Personal Computers (PC) able to support extended window TCP/IP. The Extended Window Option was designed to enable a single thread user to achieve much greater throughputs than are attainable using the current IPv4 TCP implementations. During a recent experimental effort with NASA Lewis Research Center a single TCP/IP thread was achieved that approached 400Mbps using SUN workstations with the Extended Window Option and selective acknowledgements over the ACTS satellite [5]. We will be gathering experimental and simulated results, similar to the IPv4 results presented previously, to document the improvement in throughput using an asymmetric network configuration including GBS as the forward channel. Unfortunately the Extended Window computers were not obtained early enough to support significant throughput testing in support of the JWID98 effort.

Reliable Multicast

Another solution to overcoming some inherent problems with LFN and one ideally suited for a GBS environment is reliable multicast. To support this effort we have acquired two reliable Multicast transfer programs, one COTS and one GOTS. The

COTS version is from Starburst. The GOTS version was written by NRL researchers Joseph Macker and R. Brian Adamson and contains many features not currently available in COTS versions. We have integrated these into the configuration and gathered some initial experimental results during the JWID98 effort. The ability to multicast traffic to a large number of users efficiently, reliably, and with guaranteed delivery should have significant impact on GBS. Initial results indicate that current throughput limitations are implementation specific and not protocol limited. Further work is required to quantify the effective throughput of reliable multicast in an asymmetric networked GBS environment. This work is underway.

CONCLUSIONS

The asymmetric network investigations and the resulting JWID98 effort provided an excellent data set and demonstration capability for asymmetric networking using GBS. The initial laboratory configuration with hardwired backchannel effectively bound the protocol performance with respect to latency. If asymmetric networking becomes a reality for GBS, DoD backchannel solutions will be widely varying in terms of BER and latency and it is important for researchers to know the limits of the protocol. As was demonstrated during JWID98, warfighters can use a variety of backchannels to support a GBS based asymmetric network. However, current TCP/IP v4 implementations, COTS single thread WWW browsers and COTS single thread FTP applications will not support single thread throughput approaching the GBS physical layer limits. Solutions such as extended windows are emerging and should help mitigate the effect TCP has on throughput. Clearly a reliable multicast approach to ensure data delivery to multiple sources for data that is pre-staged (i.e. pushed) will yield higher network efficiencies. Likely a combined push using reliable multicast with an extended windows solutions for applications that can not be anticipated a-priori could be the right mix to support an efficient GBS network.

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